

We are glad to welcome you to SCENARIOS' fourth newsletter!

SCENARIOS is a 4-year H2020 Research and Innovation project (RIA) involving 19 partners from 10 European countries and Israel. The goal is to close the knowledge gap and achieve breakthrough TRL advances in the toxicology, detection and remediation of probably the most objectionable and widespread class of contaminants -PFAS-, with an unprecedented energetic balance and virtually no external chemical additives. A major effort is underway to develop Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) of PFAS, including the new generation of congeners, to assist EC and EU countries in decision-making on these substances for environmental safety and human health.

SCENARIOS looks back at its achievements in the fourth year

During its fourth year of implementation, the SCENARIOS Project consolidated its scientific and technical trajectory across the three research pillars, while strengthening the translational pathway toward stakeholders and end-users. In recognition of the progress achieved and the remaining work needed to maximize impact, the project has been granted a six-month extension, moving the end date to 30 April 2026. This additional period will support completion of ongoing validation, integration of cross-pillar outputs, and preparation of final deliverables aimed at accelerating uptake by regulators, utilities, and public-health actors.

In **Pillar 1 (Smart detection)**, SCENARIOS delivered a major step forward in PFAS analytics by developing and validating three sensor-based systems tailored to different use cases and matrices. Collectively, these platforms provide complementary performance profiles, spanning from selective detection to more generic, total-estimate screening approaches. This portfolio strategy is essential in practice, because it aligns measurement tools with real life needs: rapid triage and prioritization in the field, versus compound-specific confirmation in controlled laboratory settings. A flagship result of this pillar was the completion of the human biomonitoring campaign in the Alessandria region (Italy), where an advanced Raman-SERS method was deployed in parallel with gold-standard HPLC-mass spectrometry. This paired implementation represents an important first step toward offering stakeholders a rapid and low-cost PFAS screening approach for human population monitoring, while maintaining a direct bridge to confirmatory, high-specificity analytics.

In **Pillar 2 (Mechanisms of effect and predictive toxicology)**, the project advanced from hypothesis generation to fully operational mechanistic frameworks. Mechanistic models of PFAS effects in human cellular systems were developed and implemented to provide evidence-based clues on the structural features responsible for activation of the PPAR-α receptor, strengthening structure-informed interpretation of biological potency. In parallel, SCENARIOS expanded experimental coverage using 3D cellular models of lung and intestine, screening multiple PFAS—including ether compounds, short-chain and ultra-short chain—to capture tissue-relevant responses that are often underrepresented in conventional assays. The pillar further increased molecular resolution through high-throughput transcriptomics, analyzing thousands of genes via RNA sequencing, thereby generating a data-rich foundation for pathway-level interpretation, biomarker discovery, and model refinement.

In **Pillar 3 (Remediation and treatment demonstration)**, SCENARIOS strengthened the evidence base for deployable solutions by demonstrating the high-performance SAFF system across four distinct operational settings and diverse water chemistries, including groundwater, landfill leachates, drinking water, and industrial waters. Crucially, the demonstrations incorporated co-surfactants to improve performance on short-chain PFAS, addressing a widely recognized treatment bottleneck. The system showed targeted attention to C4-C5 congeners such as PFBA, PFBS, and PFPeA, supporting the positioning of SAFF as a versatile option for real-world matrices where short-chain dominance and variable background chemistry can undermine conventional treatment performance. In parallel, SCENARIOS validated Cold Atmospheric Plasma (CAP) as a destruction technology by testing it across different reactor configurations, generating engineering-grade evidence beyond proof-of-concept. These activities showed exceptionally high PFAS destruction efficiencies alongside strong signals of economic feasibility, strengthening the case for CAP as a credible candidate for scale-up. Importantly, SAFF + CAP together constitute a groundbreaking treatment train: SAFF enables robust capture and concentration of PFAS from complex matrices, while CAP provides a true destructive endpoint for the PFAS-enriched fraction. This integrated separation-destruction strategy couples operational flexibility with ultimate risk reduction (destruction rather than phase transfer), positioning the combined train as a potentially near-universal solution for PFAS-laden wastewaters across a wide spectrum of real-world compositions.

Overall, the fourth-year achievements confirm SCENARIOS' maturation into an integrated platform spanning measurement, mechanistic understanding, and mitigation. The extension to 30 April 2026 provides the runway to consolidate these advances into actionable guidance, finalize cross-pillar integration, and ensure that validated tools and demonstrations translate into practical benefits for environmental management and public-health decision-making.

As the project is close to the conclusion of its four-year and a half journey, we are proud to look back on the milestones achieved together. Still more to come in the next months ahead.

In this newsletter, we share the most important highlights from the past year, all the academic achievements, the technological advances and our presence at international events. Most importantly, we celebrate the community of partners and stakeholders who made SCENARIOS possible.

We hope you enjoy reading our updates!

Sincerely,

The SCENARIOS Consortium

NEWS

CASSA pilot in Spain up and running

We are doing a series of trials in the CASSA site in Spain. The miniSAFF was established on February the 4th and we are now proceeding with doing multiple trials on this PFAS impacted water. The trials that we, so far, have carried out shows a low foaming water.

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SCENARIOS presented during International Day of Women and Girls in Science

Due to the successful experience of previous years UCLM scientist were invited to participate in the initiative "Interview a scientist" for the International Day of Women and Girls in Science where students in different high schools can interview women scientist.

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Seminar at FORTH delivered by Francesco Dondero

On Wednesday March 12th Prof. Francesco Dondero, Department of Science and Technological Innovation, University of Eastern Piedmont "Amedeo Avogadro" in Italy gave a talk with the title: Understanding PFAS: "Mode of Action Across Model Species, Bioaccumulation in Terrestrial and Aquatic Food Webs, and Advanced Strategies for Water Remediation".

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Third trial in Spanish pilot

During week eleventh the Envysotech team leader Say Svanström, and lab technician Kame "R&I for a Competitive Green Transition" conference that was a satellite event of the European Research and Innovation (R&I) Days 2025.

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SCENARIOS at SOS-ZEROPOL2030

The Second Living Lab workshop for the Black Sea on Exploring scenarios for reducing persistent chemicals in the Black Sea basin, took place on 8-9 April 2025 in Varna, Bulgaria. The SOS-ZEROPOL2030 event brought together regional and national administrators, experts, researchers, businesses, and NGOs with the task to assess and prioritise policies in view of their potential to raise awareness and reduce PFAS in the basin's environment.

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Students from IES Peñas Negras de Mora learn about SCENARIOS

On the 27th of May 22 students from the IES Peñas Negras de Mora in Toledo visited the laboratory at University of Castilla-La Mancha as part of the series "¿Sientes un científico por un día?": "Feel like a scientist for one day. During the three hour visit the students had the opportunity to see the work carried out in the laboratory to observe the work carried out in the SCENARIOS project.

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SCENARIOS at EuMINe training school

Konstantinos D. Papavasiliou from Novamechanics presented SCENARIOS at the EuMINe Training School – Driving Materials Innovation with Cutting-Edge Digital Platforms, Tools, and Algorithms that took place on 19-20th of June 2025 in Athens. Approximately 40 people attended the training school overall.

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R&I for a Competitive Green Transition event at Brussels

SCENARIOS project coordinator Francesco Dondero gladly accepted the invitation for the "R&I for a Competitive Green Transition" conference that was a satellite event of the European Research and Innovation (R&I) Days 2025.

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SCENARIOS presented at Population Approach Group in Europe (PAGE)

On the 5th June in Thessaloniki at the third meeting of the Population Approach Group in Europe Periklis Tsiros presented results from SCENARIOS research to members of the scientific and industry community. Around 800 attended in total, a smaller fraction came to see the poster.

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Symposium on PFAS and One Health Approach

On 20 June 2025, the interdisciplinary symposium entitled "Interdisciplinary Symposium on One Health and PFAS: an Integrated Approach to Human, Animal, and Environmental Health" took place at the Representation Hall of the University Hospital of Alessandria (AOU AL), Italy.

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First real world validation of the SCENARIOS Raman SERS platform for total PFAS detection in human serum

Between the 18th and the 1st June 2025 the Laboratory of Applied Molecular Spectroscopy (LAMS) of FORTH/ICE HT (Patras, Greece) joined forces with colleagues at the University of Eastern Piedmont (UPO, Italy) and Alessandria Hospital (AOU-AL, Italy).

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SCENARIOS at SETAC 2025

SCENARIOS was very active at SETAC 2025 that was celebrated in Vienna from the 11th to the 15th May. The Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) is a not-for-profit, worldwide professional organization with approximately 10,000 members and 21,000 followers from more than 90 countries dedicated to advancing environmental science and environmental management.

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Numerical Modeling of PFAS fate in Subsurface Workshop in PATRAS

During the 7th and 8th July at FORTH in Patras, Greece, the Numerical Modelling of PFAS fate in Subsurface Workshop took place. The first day was open to everyone while on the second day the consortium gathered together at close doors to discuss next actions.

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SCENARIOS workshop at RemTech25

SCENARIOS Project delivered outstanding workshop at RemTech 2025. The workshop "PFAS Under the Lens: Science, Solutions and Resilience – H2020-SCENARIOS" was a society success with full room capacity attendance and over 140 online participants.

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SCENARIOS at BFR International conference on PFAS

The International Conference "PFAS – Challenges and Scientific Perspectives in Human Health Risk Assessment" took place from October 8-10, 2025, in Berlin, Germany, both in-person and online. Organized by the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), the event brought together scientists and risk assessors to discuss the challenges and advances in assessing human health risks from per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS).

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SCENARIOS at EUROTOX

The EUROTOX 2025 Congress took place in Athens, Greece, from 14 to 17 September 2025, gathering researchers, regulators, and industry experts to discuss the latest advances in toxicology and chemical safety. Around 800 people attended this relevant event that connected several fields (neurotoxicity, immunotoxicity, environmental studies), and different toxicants (PFAS, pesticides, nanoplastics, nanoparticles, etc.). There was an important participation from SCENARIOS representatives presenting several outcomes from the work carried in the project.

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SCENARIOS at SENTIATECH

SENTIATECH Congress took part in Valencia, Spain on the 21st and 22nd October with over 200 professionals from the scientific community, general public, industry and policy makers sectors. SENTIATECH is an international platform focused on sustainable technologies for water, soil and environmental protection where researchers, technology providers and policymakers present advances and best practices in contamination detection and remediation.

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SCENARIOS at CE Workshop on Water Resilience

The SCENARIOS Project, represented by its Coordinator, took part in the European Commission workshop "PFAS and Waterless/Dry Coating" on 21 November 2025, contributing with a keynote intervention. The event was jointly organized by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) and the Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV) and aimed to support the definition of research and innovation priorities informing the next EU Framework Programme (FP10). The SCENARIOS contribution was positioned within the broader policy context of the Water Resilience Strategy (WRS) and the Water Resilience R&I Strategy, which frame water security and the management of emerging contaminants as priorities at the intersection of environmental protection, public health, and innovation.

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PUBLICATIONS & RESULTS

In the last year the efforts in the project have as a result several scientific publications presented at congresses and/or published on scientific journals:

- Impact of Short-Chain Perfluoropropylene Oxide Acids on Biochemical and Behavioural Parameters in Eisenia fetida (Savigny, 1826) [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Generic Method for the Detection of Short & Long Chain PFAS Extended to the Lowest Concentration Levels of SERS Capability [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Reactive Species and Mechanisms of Perfluorooctanoic Acid (Pfoa) Degradation in Water by Cold Plasma: The Role of Hv Waveform, Reactor Design, Water Matrix and Plasma Gas [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Generic method for the detection of short & long chain PFAS extended to the lowest concentration levels of SERS capability (Chemosphere journal) [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Assessment of PFAS pollution in fish and water from the United Kingdom and Spain and implications for human exposure [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Toxicological Assessment of PFAS using Seahorse Extracellular Flux Analysis [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Detection of perfluorooctance sulphonic acid in groundwater using an intelligent array of electrochemical sensors [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Evaluation of immunological impact of PFASs exposure on cytokine released and gender-based responses in PBMC [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) as environmental drivers of antimicrobial resistance: insights from genome sequences of Klebsiella grimontii and Citrobacter braakii isolated from contaminated soil [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Development of a Robust Read-Across Model for the Prediction of Biological Potency of Novel Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Delta Agonists [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Identification of two novel chemical classes of Autotaxin (ATX) inhibitors using Enalos Asclepios KNIME nodes [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Recent Advances in Computational Modeling of BACE1 Inhibitors as Anti-Alzheimer Agents [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- PFAS-Biomolecule Interactions: Case Study Using Asclepios Nodes and Automated Workflows in KNIME for Drug Discovery and Toxicology [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Multi-compound PFAS transport in the unsaturated zone during infiltration cycles [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Innovations in PFAS remediation: a review on the growing role of cold plasma technology [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- QSAR Model Development to predict PPARα activation by PFAS using human in vitro data [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Effects of Novel (Poly-) Ether PFAS on the Transcriptome of HepaRG cells [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Activation of human PPARα by mixtures of classic and novel (poly-) ether PFAS [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Transcriptomics Analysis of Novel (Poly-) Ether PFAS in HepaRG cells [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- A Multi-Route Permeability-Limited Physiologically-Based Kinetic Model for Perfluorooctanoic Acid (PFOA) Exposure of in Male and Female Rats [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- In Silico Prediction of PFAS Retention in Humans: Integrating QSAR Models for Albumin Binding and Half-Life Estimation [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Impact of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances on soil enzyme activities in Arid and Mediterranean agricultural soils [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- PFAS Exposure in Alessandria (Italy): Environmental Context, Population-Based Assessment, and Method Validation in the SCENARIOS Project [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- A Machine Learning Pipeline for estimating Binding Affinity to Serum Albumin and Half-Lives of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances in Humans [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Modelling Pharmacokinetic Variability with Physics-Informed Neural Networks [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Enhancing PFAS Risk Characterisation Through a Cloud-based PBK Model Repository [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

FORTHCOMING ACTIVITIES

SETAC Europe 36th Annual Meeting

SCENARIOS partners will hold a session at SETAC Europe 36th Annual Meeting, taking place from 17–21 May 2026 in the city of Maastricht, The Netherlands. Join fellow professionals and students at this premier environmental science event, explore the theme "Embrace the Outlier: In Science, Regulations, and Networks," and present your research on an international stage.

Session Title: PFAS Across the Environment–Human Continuum: From Molecular Mechanisms to Disease-Relevant Outcomes
Track: 1. Environmental and Human Toxicology: From Molecules to Organisms, From Omics to in Vivo

Lead Chair: Francesco, Dondero, University of Eastern Piedmont, Italy
Co-Chairs: Iseult Lynch, University of Birmingham United Kingdom and Antreas Afantitis, Entelos Institute Cyprus

[▶ Contact us for more information!](#)

<https://scenarios-project.eu/>

